

Deliverable D 8.1

Communication Plan, Data Management Plan and Project Identity kit

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Deliverable type and dissemination level	
Report	PU - Public

1 INTRODUCTION INTO THE COMMUNICATION PLAN

Objectives

To successfully fulfil the project objectives it is essential to establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely communication. Therefore, a comprehensive communication plan is needed. As well as a broad and targeted distribution of project information, the communication plan will include a guide for internal communications. To this end, the project activities, both inside and outside, of the consortium will be promoted during the whole project lifecycle.

The objectives of the communication plan are:

- Set guidelines for the internal and external communication;
- Provide a graphical identity kit that are key elements for the corporate design;
- Communication measures with different target groups;
- Formats for target-oriented information of stakeholders;
- Encouragement of collaboration and interactions between consortium partners;
- Coordination of all levels, types and tools of communication as well as responsibilities in relation to the project; and
- Regulations on the dissemination of the project results.

Guiding Principles

To achieve the above-mentioned objectives the communication plan must be clear and known to all of the consortium partners.

The scope of communication and responsibilities will be defined so that all team members know their functions, see here respective chapters in the GREENPEG Consortium Agreement. In addition, communication and dissemination must be useful and target-driven. All communication must be honest, open and available to the intended target audience. It is important to create an environment within the Project that enables free, open communication between all Project Members and not just a top-down approach followed. Transparency plays an important role in project communication as it forms an essential part of ensuring that public money is used throughout. To ensure a high level of transparency an efficient information and communication flow is needed. This is made possible through easy access to relevant information about the programme requirements and administrative procedures, such as described in the Data Management Plan with regard to the implementation and performance of the GREENPEG e-forum. Moreover, it is necessary to inform about the project progress and its value to the community and the European Union in an accurate and timely manner. The achievements of the project must be advertised and published.

The aim of communication

The European Commission has stored comprehensive information on internet how to communicate a project (8,10). The topics range from what we want to achieve, being creative, define target audience, identify relevant media people, think issue – not project (with regard to non-professional target groups) showing society the impact of the project, building a brand. These guiding principles of communication will be achieved by the following measures.

2.1 Graphical Identity

To differentiate GREENPEG from other projects a corporate identity (CI) has been developed. Through its CI GREENPEG will develop a brand identity that will become imbedded in the stakeholders' minds. Integral to forming this identity, is communication, behaviour, language, philosophy as well as design. To facilitate this, an anchoring visual image (corporate design) has been created.

The GREENPEG identity comprises:

1. Logo,
2. Fonts,
3. Colours,
4. Text; and an
5. Entry Image

2.1.1 GREENPEG Logo

The GREENPEG logo is a visual identity that is composed of the different elements that constitute the project. These combine an electrical plug in reference to renewable energy GREENPEG target commodities are referring to. The poles of the plug represent in micro scale the elongated spodumene crystals and in macro scale the elongated pegmatites bodies. The color of the plug and poles in the version shown in figure 2.1 are taken from the colors of the two greenish and pinkish Lithium bearing Spodumene crystal varieties. The text "GREENPEG", written in black represents the cable of the plug and one screw is the registered trade mark sign. The Logo will be available in 5 different color and monochrome settings as illustrated in figure 2.2. They will allow to highlight the logo on multi-colored, white and black background. The GREENPEG Logo was developed by Wolfgang Reimer, GKZ, and approved by the Steering Committee during the KOM. With the scope and potential of the GREENPEG project to uncover innovations and inventions during its research, consideration must be given to registering the Logo. Investigations are under way with the European Patent Office on how best to protect the brand identity (e.g. word and figurative mark).

Figure 2.1: GREENPEG Logo for use on white background in color prints and digital media

Font used for "GREENPEG" is DIN

Farbig

Negativ – farbig

Negativ – einfarbig

Schwarz-Weiß

Schwarz-Grau

Figure 2.2: GREENPEG logo versions. All the data needed for print and reproduction are provided as the GREENPEG Style Sheet at www.greenpeg.eu.

Pantone 7742 CP
 CMYK 71/28/96/13
 RGB 85/131/54
 HTML #558336

Pantone 5527 CP
 CMYK 20/0/30/5
 RGB 208/224/190
 HTML #d0e0be

Pantone 7520 CP
 CMYK 0/20/30/0
 RGB 252/215/184
 HTML #fcd7b8

Anthrazit
 CMYK 69/60/56/66
 RGB 51/50/51
 HTML #333233

Anthrazit Deckkraft 50%
 CMYK 69/60/56/66
 RGB 51/50/51
 HTML #333233

Anthrazit Deckkraft 20%
 CMYK 69/60/56/66
 RGB 51/50/51
 HTML #333233

Figure 2.3: GREENPEG Logo Colors

2.1.2 GREENPEG Partner Banner

The GREENPEG Partner logos have been arranged to compose a GREENPEG Partner Banner. The Banner will be used as a graphics element in a number of templates for dissemination and beyond, e.g. in print media as background in venues or any other documentation where the Consortium should be highlighted.

Figure 2.4: GREENPEG Partner Banner

2.1.3 EU Emblem

As well as the GREENPEG logo we will be using the authorised EU Emblem (9) in all communication and dissemination activities. The EU Emblem must be used according to the European Commissions' guidelines, which are found here: <https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/section/communication-toolkit>

Figure 2.4: EU Emblem with reference to GREENPEG GA No.

All project partners agree to the use of these agreed graphic elements when presenting the project or project results.

2.1.4. GREENPEG Email account

GREENPEG Web site will be using the email account info@greenpeg.eu.

2.2 Templates for Documents and Reports

To facilitate standardized communication of the project both internally and externally templates have been produced for all text documents (agendas, minutes, reports, press releases, letters). In addition, a Power Point presentation template has been created thereby ensuring conformity for all types of output. These templates ensure uniformity of the corporate image of the project and will establish a visual language that indicates, at a glance, that the presented information concerns GREENPEG. These templates determine where and how the graphical elements are to be arranged within the documents, especially on the cover page, the fonts and spaces to be used, and so on. All templates will be accessible on project share site (e-forum) and all of the Project Partners are to use them. All templates can be found in Appendix.

The Font of all working documents and reports is Calibri 11 with line spacing set at multiple 1.15.

2.3 Fonts for GREENPEG Web Site

The Font being used for the Internet presentation of GREENPEG is Roboto Condensed + Styles

GREENPEG | Font Roboto Condensed + Styles

- | | |
|--|--|
| Roboto Condensed Light | • Weit hinten, hinter den Wortbergen, fern der Länder Vokalien und Konsonantien leben die Blindtexte. Abgeschieden wohnen sie in Buchstabenhäusern an der Küste des Semantik, eines großen Sprachozeans. |
| Roboto Condensed Light Italic | • <i>Ein kleines Bächlein namens Duden fließt durch ihren Ort und versorgt sie mit den nötigen Regelialien. Es ist ein paradiesmatisches Land, in dem einem gebratene Satzteile in den Mund fliegen.</i> |
| Roboto Condensed Regular | • Nicht einmal von der allmächtigen Interpunktion werden die Blindtexte beherrscht – ein geradezu unorthographisches Leben. Eines Tages aber beschloß eine kleine Zeile Blindtext, ihr Name war Lorem Ipsum, hinaus zu gehen in die weite Grammatik. |
| <i>Roboto Condensed Regular Italic</i> | • <i>Der große Oxmox riet ihr davon ab, da es dort wimmelte von bösen Kommata, wilden Fragezeichen und hinterhältigen Semikoli, doch das Blindtextchen ließ sich nicht beirren. Es packte seine sieben Versalien, schob sich sein Initial in den Gürtel und machte sich auf den Weg.</i> |
| Roboto Condensed Bold | • Als es die ersten Hügel des Kursivgebirges erklommen hatte, warf es einen letzten Blick zurück auf die Skyline seiner Heimatstadt Buchstabenhausen, die Headline von Alphabetdorf und die Subline seiner eigenen Straße, der Zeilengasse. |
| <i>Roboto Condensed Bold Italic</i> | • <i>Wehmütig lief ihm eine rhetorische Frage über die Wange, dann setzte es seinen Weg fort. Unterwegs traf es eine Copy.</i> |

3 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

3.1 Communication Objectives set up by the GREENPEG Project

Communication activities comprise dissemination measures for promoting the project and its findings during the whole period of the grant. All measures will be proportionate to the scale of the project, with clear objectives. The dissemination measures will be tailored to the needs of the various target audiences, which will include groups beyond the project's own community. This will include measures for public/societal engagement on issues related to the project, such as: raw material awareness building, education and training.

The primary communication language will be English.

To enable sufficient time for this to take place deliverables must be sent to the coordinator for review a minimum of 10 working days before their deliverable due date.

There are two communication strategies: internal and external. Internal communication consists of communication between the GREENPEG partners within the project as well as the definition of their roles and responsibilities. External communication relates to communication with the different external stakeholders, e.g. public authorities, policy makers, and various target groups.

3.1.1 Internal Communication

Internal communication facilitates the communication between project partners. Everybody needs to have clear and defined roles and an understanding of project aims within the consortium. This enables identification with the project which in turn will increase motivation and engagement in the project. Relevant measures to steer the project that way are described in the GREENPEG Consortium Agreement.

3.1.2 External Communication

External communication presents information about the project to target audiences. It is necessary to identify different stakeholders and adjust the information according to the audience. This includes adjusting language, wording, content and medium. These adjustments will assist in promoting value of GREENPEG to wider community and relevant stakeholders. The main objective is to promote GREENPEG as a beneficial project which adds value to the EU and society. Through the use of different external communication channels it will be possible to build and strengthen regular contact with the media.

3.2 Target Group

A project with a diverse network comprising industry partners, research and academic partners addresses different interests which are represented by various stakeholders. These stakeholders can be internal or external.

The main target groups are as follows:

Project Partners and Associated Institutions (internal stakeholder):

- General Assembly and Steering Committee of GREENPEG;
- Working Groups and project partners of GREENPEG;
- Advisory Board and members of the GREENPEG Think Tank
- Associated partners of GREENPEG;
- European Union institutions.

General Public:

- Citizens from the research area, especially in the region of our test sites;
- Students and professionals;
- National and transnational professionals; and
- EU general public.

Media:

- Local, regional, national and EU-level and specialised media (print, online).

Institutions:

- National, regional and local authorities;
- Universities, schools and research organisations;
- Relevant Institutions, networks, organisations, decision-makers, NGOs (in the raw material sector); and
- Governmental bodies.

Professionals:

- Potential applicants of GREENPEG technologies from industry;
- Exploration and Mining Industry Practitioners;
- Specialised professional networks;
- Research institutes; and
- Business associations.

3.3 Messages

It is necessary to inform the different stakeholders about the programme, its background, objectives, procedures, benefits and results. The delivery of the information has to be adjusted according to the stakeholder group.

Thus, messages relating to the stakeholders need to be formulated. These comprise all messages including flyers, messages on the website, general information about the project in presentations and publications etc. The messages should consist of highlights of GREENPEG project.

The Key messages to be transmitted are:

- What the project is about;
- Project aims and objectives;
- Potential impact of the project;
- Who is involved in the project (partner, associated and affiliated partner);
- Project conferences, workshops and events;
- Major developments; and
- Key milestones of the project.

Emotional attraction

Another message is how the Project emotionally attracts in combination with a story telling which is considered to be especially a subject of the GREENPEG web site. The HOME site of the GREENPEG web site has been designed to provide the visitor a message. This message will be drawn from the image (a landscape photo of the Tysfjord mountains (close to one test site) in the background with a green carpet of wool grass in the foreground which symbolizes the “Greening”.

In combination with the wording of the Web Site phrase: “Join us feeding the energy transition” and the keywords of the lower pull down menus: “Discover” “Pegmatites” “In Europe” the GREENPEG web site entry message is quite clear: “Join us feeding the energy transition – discover pegmatites in Europe”. The Tysfjord image of the HOME page will be repeated in the Power Point presentation cover page.

4 COMMUNICATION TOOLS

The communication plan lists a variety of communication tools to be used depending on the situation. These communication tools can be used both internally and externally and adjusted accordingly to meet the needs of the target audience.

4.1 Internal Communication Tools

Internal Communication is the communication (both verbal and written) between the partners within the project, with the aim of promoting optimal cooperation and exchange of information between them. The activities and tools to be used to facilitate communication are listed below:

4.1.1 Meetings

Meetings are an extremely important communication tool, due to their interactive nature. They can open up opportunities for networking as well as the provision of media opportunities. There will be several events which will serve the needs of specific target groups and depending on the event objectives these meetings may also be open to the public. There may be a requirement for additional work package meetings to be arranged/held. Any formal conclusions made at these meetings must be shared with the Steering Committee. Aside the regular opportunities for the GREENPEG SEAB members to attend the meetings GREENPEG will be holding also brain-storming sessions in which ideas will be evaluated by a strong industrial led panel who will rationalise and channel progress without sacrificing quality with the overall GREENPEG project goals in mind. The GREENPEG Think Tank has been chosen as an appropriate format to integrate end-user experience.

Physical and online meetings, online meeting software

Meetings will be held at various locations across the project but equally they can be held by video or teleconference. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and legislative measures (such as travel ban, social distancing) the way meetings will be carried out will be subject to the present and expected bans on traveling, assembly and other barriers by EC and EU member state regulations.

As a consequence thereof the *GREENPEG Kick-Off Meeting* has been held on 4 June 2020 as an online conference participated by the project partners and the GREENPEG project officer only.

During the Kick-Off the general assembly agreed on using →*MICROSOFT TEAMS as the principal online conference tool.*

Focus Group Meetings

Focus Group Meetings are an essential tool to familiarise end users and other stakeholders with the research and socio-economic environment of the consortium. They will be held at three of the four demonstration test sites according to the GREENPEG meetings schedule. This includes also measures of raising raw material awareness of locals in the respective region. These workshops give the opportunity to discuss the project results so far and to inform the broader public of the project objectives, this makes it not only an external communication tool but also works toward the GREENPEG objective of raising public raw material awareness. GREENPEG feels obliged to inform the public about the project and its background as exploration and mining are an integral part of our modern society. GREENPEG aims to raise public raw material awareness and promote the acceptance of environmentally friendly exploration and mining. Thus, focus group discussions offer the opportunity to get in contact with different target groups.

Meetings	Month, (duration incl. travel)	Venue	Participants (Responsible WP leader)	Theme/Target group
Kick-off meeting	4 June 2020	Virtual meeting	All partners (WP1)	GREENPEG strategy refinement, implementation of project, WP presentation and coordination of project implementation
1. Progress meeting, SC	25-28 August 2020 (4)	Drag, Norway with demonstration site visit in Tysfjord	All partners, AB (WP1)	GREENPEG demonstration site in Norway, sampling strategy refinement for geophysical and geochemical exploration; project steering
Regional Kick Off Meeting	24 November 2020 (1)	Dresden, Germany	UiO, TERRA, IFU, PNO DE (WP8)	Presentation of the GREENPEG tasks and role to local stakeholders and policy makers
1. Think Tank Meeting	April 2021 (3)	London	All WP leaders, AB (WP8)	Trend analysis, Identification of strategic concepts, solutions for specific problem cases and/or product innovations, market review
2. Progress meeting, 1. Focus Group Meeting	September 2021 (6)	Graz, Austria, with field demonstration site visit in Wolfsberg	SC, GA, AB, All partners (WP1, WP8)	GREENPEG demonstration site in Austria; WP presentation, evaluation of first exploration results; project steering, WP progress presentation, Focus Group (multipliers, end user civil society)
2. Think Tank Meeting	February 2022 (3)	Freiberg, GKZ	SC, AB, All WP leaders (WP8, WP1)	Trend analysis, Identification of strategic concepts, solutions for specific problem cases and/or product innovations, market review, project steering

1. Exploitation Seminar	April 2022 (2)	Brussels, Saxon Liaison Office, RV1	All partners (WP8)	GREENPEG exploitation and dissemination, first audit review by EC
3. Progress meeting; 2. Focus Group Meeting	September 2022 (5)	Dublin, Ireland, with demonstration site visit in Leinster	All partners, AB (WP4, WP8)	GREENPEG demonstration site in Ireland, preliminary establishment of exploration tool-sets; project steering, WP progress presentation, Focus Group (multipliers, end user civil society)
3. Think Tank Meeting; 2. Exploitation Seminar Raw Materials Week	December 2022 (3)	Heitersheim	Project Partners on demand, SC, AB (WP8)	Trend analysis, Identification of strategic concepts, solutions for specific problem cases and/or product innovations, market review; GREENPEG exploitation and dissemination, Raw Materials Week Satellite Event
RV2, GREENPEG Cluster Conference	April 2023 (2)	Brussels Liaison Office of Italy / Saxony	All WP leaders (WP1, WP8)	second audit review by EC, Clustering
4. Progress meeting (all partners) and 3. Focus Group Meeting (SC only)	July 2023 (3)	Porto	All partners (WP1, WP8)	GREENPEG meeting in Portugal, establishment of exploration tool-sets; project steering, WP progress presentation, Focus Group (multipliers, end user civil society)
Raw Material Week	December 2023 (2)	Brussels	Relevant partners (WP1, WP8)	Participation Raw Materials Week
Project closure meeting	April 2024 (3)	Oslo	All partners	Preparation of final reports

Table 1: Schedule of project meetings and common field visits. AB – Expert Advisory Board; GA – General Assembly; SC – Steering Committee by 13 June 2020

Recording of Meetings

All formal meetings, including telephone or video conference, must be minuted. These can be done either by using the Meeting Minutes or Telephone Message Template or by following up a telephone conversation with an email that reiterates the key facts of the conversation.

Minutes of meetings are to be circulated to all those that attended the meeting, plus those that were to attend but could not make it (following the guidelines set out in the Consortium Agreement). In addition, Work Package meetings must also be circulated to the Project Coordinator and the Project Manager. The Project Coordinator will then decide whether the minutes should also be disseminated to the Steering Committee.

Minutes of	Send to
General Assembly	All partners as well as Associate Partners
Steering Committee	Members of the Steering Committee
Work Package Meeting	Work Package Leaders and Steering Committee

Table 4.1: Distribution list.

The minutes of all meetings and any other official GREENPEG correspondence should be distributed according to the Distribution List in Table 4.1 above and only sent to other parties with the approval of the Project Coordinator and the Project Manager.

The minutes should be decision oriented on the base of the topic and questions raised and solutions and demand for action (to be) taken.

4.1.2 Internal Communication Platform

Since the GREENPEG consortium brings together highly complementary and multi-disciplinary research teams, it is vital that each team communicates its own, often highly specialised expertise, in such a manner that it feeds the research needs of other participants in the consortium, in the most effective manner.

WP1 will be investigating the use of an e-forum / intranet package that will help to ensure that effective transfer of knowledge from one work package to another can take place. This e-forum / intranet shall facilitate internal communication between the project members. For example, it will be possible to exchange documents as well as write notes on informal conversations during a telephone or video conference. In addition, it will be capable to store extensive meta data, thus combining an Electronic Management System (EMS) with a Depository of the data management. The access will be granted by a username and password for all Project Partners.

The following items will be available:

- General Project documents;
- Graphical identity elements;
- Calendar;
- Chatroom;
- Time schedule; and
- Depending on the security standards, deliverables should also be stored on the internal web site (e-forum).

4.1.3 Internal Communication

All project partners are advised to carry out and to archive their correspondence properly:

The titling / syntax of the emailing subject matter to be used is:

GREENPEG WP (no) Task (no) (subject).

e.g. GREENPEG WP8 T8.1 events calendar update

The syntax for file names will be as follows:

(YYMMDD) (GREENPEG) (WP) (no) (subject). suffix

e.g. 210213 GREENPEG WP 4 sample list.xls

Response Times, Contact Database, Calendar

It is obligatory to answer mail or phone requests in due time – either by the responsible person or by proxy. More information on the timing is given in the GREENPEG Consortium Agreement. A spreadsheet will be developed where the responsible person and their proxy are listed, so that everybody knows who is accountable. This spreadsheet will be circulated throughout all the Project Partners.

A contact database has been compiled which outlines the main administrative and technical contacts of the Project Partners. This document will be held on the share site (e-forum) and updated as changes occur.

The Timeline for the project will also be held on the share site. It will show the Deliverables, Tasks, Deliverable Dates, Milestones and Meeting Dates.

In addition, there will be a project calendar. As well as holding the key deliverable deadlines all key project and work package members are advised to indicate their holidays and absences. This will assist when planning and coordinating events. Everyone is responsible for keeping their information up-to-date. The project management team will oversee the calendar.

4.2 External Communication Tools

The objective of external communication is to maximise the value and awareness of the project outcomes to a wide range of target groups. Therefore, different activities and tools provide adequate opportunities to disseminate project information. The GREENPEG selected tools and activities are as follows:

4.2.1 Project Identity Communication Tools

A graphical identity (logo) has been created, details of which are contained in Chapter 2.1. This logo has been designed to give a visual element that has been designed to be instantly recognisable and synonymous with the GREENPEG project.

→ This logo must be used on all documentation and correspondence whether online or in print form, both internally and externally (except E-Mail communication).

4.2.2 GREENPEG Meetings

Focus Group Meetings

The focus group meetings will provide an opportunity to get in contact with different target groups, e.g. residents of the test / reference sites. One important task of GREENPEG is to raise the public raw material awareness and to inform about the project and its background. Detailed information about focus group meetings is contained in chapter 4.1 - Internal Communication Tools (meetings).

Final Conference

At the end of the project a conference will be held to disseminate results and experiences from the project to relevant stakeholder communities and identify pathways for future research and sustainability of project outputs (where appropriate). Time and place will be decided upon the conference planning aiming at synergies with other events and in order to increase the visibility and impact of the closure conference.

4.2.3 Online Based Communication

Project Website

Websites present an inevitable channel for information dissemination especially towards the general public. The web site of the project will be the front end, i.e. the public image of the project. The site will allow users to readily collect online information about the project which might be of interest to the various stakeholders. The project web presence will be designed and implemented during the first six months of the project, with more content added as the project develops. This public web site will be in English and will provide an information point for the work of the Project itself.

The Layout and structure of the GREENPEG Website considers the latest trends in web design and target group specific preferences. In the same way the Website tries to open new ways of conveying messages and using a mix of state-of-the-art stock photos and pictures taken from the project implementation and the Project Partners archives. The Website will be also more readable if not to say entertaining by combining fact based information with a distinct poetry by phrases on the entry side images of the submenus. This – aside the composition of the entry HOME site another measure to give the GREENPEG a certain spirit and to make the site different and recognizable.

Figure 4.1: The portal of the GREENPEG web site currently under construction.

The following content will be included in the website:

- Project description; aims and objectives
- Project approach and workplan
- Details of partners (with links to partners' web site);
- Regions / test sites
- News & Media Corner
- Project results for the public domain;
- Interim results and working papers for the public domain;
- Public deliverables (e.g. newsletter, video, publications, etc.);
- Events (Public);
- Contacts; and
- Links to other projects, services, collaborative efforts, etc. relevant to each part of the project.

The public web site will be the “meeting point for all target groups” and one of the main channels for wider public information dissemination. It will contain some of the information that is also available on the project share site, subject to partners’ agreement. The web site will provide an option for interested people to register for additional information and the newsletter service.

The GREENPEG homepage will be used both as an internal and external communication tool.

The GREENPEG domain acquired for the portal is: www.greenpeg.eu

In order to achieve its objectives, the web site will be regularly updated. The portal will be highly transparent, well-structured and user friendly, making it easy for visitors to find the information they require.

Social Media

The important task of raising public raw material awareness requires an age-oriented dissemination. One possibility to achieve this objective is the use of social media. According (10) social media are a great way to keep up-to-date with what's going on in our community and to contribute own views. This will provide an interactive dialogue with the online audience. Options being considered are: YouTube videos and Twitter. The application of these tools need to be evaluated by purpose to determine which are the most suitable to meet the needs of the project. More than this social media will be part of clustering, using also the accounts provided by the Commission.

The GREENPEG Twitter account will be registered after the GREENPEG website is fully online

Project Newsletter (E-Bulletin)

During the GREENPEG Project lifecycle a bi-annual newsletter “The GREENPEG E-Bulletin” will be distributed. The Newsletter will contain the graphics elements giving the Bulletin the GREENPEG Corporate Design. The content of the Newsletter will comprise the following categories:

- Forward from the editor and a selected project partner (it is intended that every partner will be considered)
- New publications;
- New events;
- News from the Work Package Leaders;
- Achievements in research and innovation; and
- Editorial.

The newsletter will feature relevant news on the projects progress, project partners, related initiatives and industry and EU news. The newsletter is a good forum to feed the partner network (both internal and external) with relevant information. Each GREENPEG project member is encouraged to support the newsletter's development by providing written statements and articles or further suggestions for content. It is envisaged to print physical copies for mail in limited number. The number of issues to be released and the responsible person will be decided during the first six months of the project.

4.2.4 Press Releases and Articles

To ensure transparency of project activities, media will be informed about all project activities and will be invited to project events, such as conferences or focus group workshops that are also for the public. Partners should be mindful of marketable results from meetings and project results and produce a press release text which can be sent to the media.

The official Press Release Template must be used for all announcements (see Appendix). All press releases must be sent to the Project Coordinator and the Project Manager for approval and to inform the Project Officer, prior to their release.

Official press releases must be in English.

If press releases need to be published in national languages, the relevant national project partner is responsible for translation and dissemination of the press release. However, the Project Partners must inform the Project Coordinator and Project Manager about the all press releases (national and international) by sending them the original press release and the place(s) of publication.

4.2.5 Print Media

Printed information about projects are important as means of sharing information. The planned publications should include both specialised publications and general publications which are simple, concise, illustrated and will show the practical implications of the programme for the citizens in the target regions and the EU. All published materials will follow the Corporate Design of GREENPEG. Many of the printed materials will be available for download in electronic format, especially on the GREENPEG website. A "print on demand" strategy will contribute to maximising the results while reducing expenses.

Scientific Publications

Scientific publications are a major key to maximising the impact of the Projects results whilst economically advertising the developed technologies and their potential use and attracting industry,

close target groups and end users within the EU and EU associated partner countries. The main forms of scientific dissemination will be through articles in peer-reviewed journals, professional journals, presentations at leading conferences and trade fairs. In the first instance all these publications will be sent to the Project Coordinator and the Project Manager.

Project Flyer, Banners, Posters, etc.

A project flyer, with an introduction to the project and contact information, will be produced within the first months of the project. The motto is: “Quality rather than Quantity” which means the design and content of the flyer is more important than the number of copies. The project flyer will contain a project overview, a list of partners, an overview of the project structure and objectives as well as contact information. The design should be captivating to emphasise the relevance of GREENPEG, and giving the appearance of quality. The flyer will be delivered to the project partners, members of the GREENPEG SEAB and GREENPEG Think Tank as well as to important stakeholders.

In addition, a public information banners and posters will also be created to promote the visibility and recognition of the GREENPEG project. They will set up in the GREENPEG Corporate Design.

4.2.6 The GREEN BOOK

As part of the public awareness, building GREENPEG will compose a special photo story of young careers activities during the GREENPEG student summer school. This is an activity of GREENPEG to introduce young careers into the World of Exploration by a cross-European students exchange programme connecting academic and industrial organisations through the conduction of a one-month Summer School in year 3 of the project.

The photo story is published in the →GREEN BOOK. It aims at contributing to the societal challenge of climate protection and mining in context of the UN Sustainable Development Goals / Agenda 2030. A professional peoples photographer will be hired for the portrait photo shooting.

In analogy to the similar Booklet “Faces of FAME” from HORIZON 2020 project FAME, grant number 641650, the GREEN BOOK will be edited as a commitment to “life the European idea” documenting students self-image, commitment to Europe and attitude to Raw Materials in the light of the ambitious European GREEN DEAL agenda and global challenges in climate and supply chains.

4.2.7 Fair and Exhibition

Establishing a constructive dialogue with end users will be an important aspect towards gaining the acceptance of the new products and services by those stakeholders who would be in a position to exploit the results as part of their portfolio of services and / or the commercial manufacturing and commissioning of the new GREENPEG products. The most important conference / exhibition events will be subject to the GREENPEG event calendar which will be regularly updated by all Project Partners.

4.2.8 Additional External Communication

In addition to these communication activities classical face to face dialogues or any kind of direct contact outside the project might help to increase GREENPEG's visibility and recognition. Many project partners regularly attend national and international events, e.g. EU events, scientific conferences etc. where they can talk about GREENPEG with other relevant stakeholders in administration, research and industry and spread knowledge of the project objectives and results. This will enlarge the network and can be very beneficial in terms of future research.

Special emphasis will be taken to consider EC and HORIZON 2020 programme formats such as the annual Raw Materials Day or events organized by the European Cluster Collaboration Platform as well as distinctive Raw Materials panels such as EUROMINES, ETP SMR and the future CoMMER (Council of Mining and Metallurgy Regions in EU) to physically present the GREENPEG project and the results. More than this every Project Partner is advised to contribute to national events or those from projects and project clustering of EU grant programs.

4.2.9 Media Partnership

GREENPEG Project considers to enter in media partnerships to share content for a mutual benefit. This can be an effective promotional vehicle that can bring good publicity for both partners. The key is to establish a partnership with a media outlet whose readership is similar to the GREENPEG professional target audience. This helps Partners to create content for the media outlet that resonates with its readers.

GREENPEG will carefully weight what the Project wants to achieve from the media partnership(s), e.g. to reach a certain number of viewers or readers, or to link the website to the articles on the media outlet's website to raise more landings on GREENPEG homepage and to make the Project and its output more known. This will be also a question of how many opportunities one needs to share content or whether setting up a campaign where one can contribute one piece of content per month for the outlet's audience would generate the best impact (6). This will be also balanced against the maneuver space with other, similar partnerships and subject to a steady measure and reevaluation of the resulted impact and the performance of the media partnership. In this regard the approach to a media partnership can consider a strategic plan with the media partner, define key messages GREENPEG wants to share based on the outlined goals.

5 EVALUATION AND QUALITY MANAGEMENT

To ensure the quality and quantity of communication tools to be used it is necessary to monitor and evaluate the implemented media. The main purpose of the evaluation is to figure out how effective the information and publicity measures are in terms of visibility and awareness of GREENPEG. Following these evaluations communication tools and activities could be improved upon. In addition, to ensure the quality of any communication activity various skills will need to be proofed, e.g. writing skills, presentation skills and management skills.

5.1 Evaluation of Communication Activities

For the process of monitoring and evaluating the communication activities set in the communication plan both quantitative and qualitative indicators will be used. The evaluation will be undertaken continuously in order to allow possible corrections of the plan during the project phase. The project management team as well as all partners who are responsible for different communication activities will be involved in the evaluation process.

The evaluation will comprise positive or negative media coverage, sustainability of media and their impact as well as internal communication channels and analysis of emerging problems.

Different evaluation tools will be used such as evaluation, questionnaires, online surveys or focus group discussions/interviews with project partners or others to determine the level of satisfaction of various target groups and to adjust the dissemination list.

It will also be important to measure the impact of used communication tools such as the impact of events. These can be evaluated through the number of participants in project events or the number of articles about GREENPEG in the media which again will be part of the dissemination list layout.

The website impact can also be evaluated easily through website analysis tools measuring the number of visitors to the site, pages visited most on the website, duration, and the number of downloads of the available online materials. We will be using Google Analytics which provides a suitable tool to measure website traffic on a monthly reporting sheet.

To test the impact of publications the number of produced publications or the numbers of copies requested and distributed will be helpful. Additionally, the impact factor of journals where articles may be submitted can give an indication about the quality and influence of the journal.

Evaluation of the communication tools and activities will give the project coordinator and manager and WP8 leader a good idea which tools are effective and should be repeated. This could increase the visibility of GREENPEG and help to achieve the project aims.

5.2 Quality Management

One important point of quality management is to determine responsibilities. Each partner must know his tasks, his responsible work packages and his function in project management, communication and dissemination. A lot of different tools and measures are already explained in this communication plan, e.g. the time schedule for project work or the internal channel of communication.

The main responsibility for the communication and dissemination of the GREENPEG Project is held with the project coordination and management (University of Oslo, Norway) and Leader WP8 (GKZ Freiberg, Germany).

All project partners are committed to supporting communication and dissemination of the GREENPEG project results in order to increase GREENPEG's visibility and reputation. Effective communication could lead to a more rapid and easier dissemination of project results. All members of the consortium are responsible for the reporting, publications, news and media coverage connected with their activities in the project as well as with potentially interested target groups in the EC and overseas.

5.2.1 Writing Skills

Scientific Writing

Scientific publications are crucial for maximising the impact of the GREENPEG results. Therefore, it is helpful to identify standard quality requirements for publications. The following aspects need to be considered when conducting scientific writing:

- Topic must be of great interest;
- Very professional presentation of novel data that needs to be published;
- Topic is of broad international and generic interest, so that the article is suitable for publication;
- The article shall attract a high number of downloads and citations;
- Article must have novelty;
- The quality of interpretations and conclusions shall be high;
- The technical aspects shall be respected: paper should be properly organised, to the point and concise, written clearly using a correct grammar and syntax;
- Title needs to be informative and a reflection of the content;
- The illustrations and tables are useful and of good quality; and
- The references must be relevant and up to date.

Writing for the Press

The main purpose when writing for the press is to catch the attention of the different media channels. The following things need to be considered when writing press releases or articles for press media:

- Writing must be simple and short. Journalists rapidly scan press releases to detect newsworthy subjects that they could write an article about following the motto: 'Brevity is the soul of wit';
- Include the quotes of important people (major players) in the relevant field. It will humanise the article;
- Underpinning the press release with data and numbers to increase the credibility of the story;
- Integrating the contact to maximise the visibility of GREENPEG; and
- Including hints with links to additional information, e.g. to GREENPEG website.

There is a good background information on how to write a press release on the following web site (7): <https://bizfluent.com/13725244/press-releases-uses-results-for-small-business-owners>

Writing for the Web

Writing for the web requires simple and short sentences containing information that is easy to understand. Bullet points can facilitate reading. Additionally, an eye-catching headline helps to attract interest and readers. One should use simple words that are part of everyone's language. How to write appropriately for the web depends also on the specific target groups. Writing for youths or students differentiates from writing for professionals or scientists. Be aware of these specifications and do not miss to add a meaningful photo that combines environment-technology-humans in an extraordinary way.

5.2.2. Presentation Skills

Presenting information in a clear and effective manner is essential to getting your message across. Especially in the scientific arena where the presentation of project results is crucial for informing target groups about their achievements. Therefore, it is not only the content and structure of the presentation that must be appropriate but also the style of presentation, vocabulary and language needs to be adjusted for the target audience. Presenting in an appropriate tone, pitch and volume of voice will add emphasis and maintain the interest of the audience. It is important to hold eye contact with the audience. In some cases, it can be helpful to include media into the presentation to illustrate the spoken words, e.g. videos or pictures relating to the content of the presentation.

5.2.3 Organising Events

Events and public project meetings must be published early enough so that the press and interested parties have the chance to participate. During the event, it is important to allow the press to hold interviews and write a press release. If the press is not present at the event, a press release must be published immediately after the event.

6. DISSEMINATION

The dissemination of the communication plan is divided into three strategic focus areas, so that the focus is based on where and when the effort of the dissemination is most needed and will be most effective. The strategic focus areas are:

- Dissemination at local level;
- Dissemination at National level; and
- Dissemination at European level.

Dissemination Level	Means of Communication	Target Groups
Local level	Brochure, Flyer, Internet website, Press releases, Articles, Local focus group workshops, Company visits /site visits.	SMEs, Geo service providers, Professional associations presented at local level, Universities, schools and students, Municipalities and regional administrations, Citizens in the deposit area.
National level	Brochure, Flyer, Internet website, Press releases, Articles, Focus group workshops, Events, Networking and face to face dialogues.	SMEs , Geo service providers, Professional associations, National public authorities, Universities, schools and students, Research organizations, platforms National Geological Surveys Society.
European level	Brochure, Flyer, Internet website, Press releases, Articles and scientific publications, Focus group workshops, Events, Networking and face to face dialogues, Attendance at EU events, International conferences, Internal and public meetings of the project.	Consortium member, Europe network, European Commission and European administrations, SMEs, Universities and research organisations, Professional associations, platforms, Society.

Dissemination will be based on a stakeholder database which is the key source for a central mailing according to the specified dissemination level, means of communication and target groups. The stakeholder data base will be jointly developed by WP1, WP7 and WP8 leaders in accordance with GDPR requirements.

ResearchGate

ResearchGate is a professional network where scientists and researchers can share and access scientific content, knowledge, and expertise. 15 million researchers and scientists connect on the network with peers to share and discover science as it happens. They have made more than 140 million connections, shared new developments in over one million ongoing research projects, and post half a million updates about their work daily.

[GREENPEG project is registered at ResearchGate via the GREENPEG Coordinator](#)

7. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

7.1 Aim and Objectives

A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon 2020 project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

The aim of the DMP is to provide a positive stimulus to thinking about how the data generated within a project will be stored, managed and safeguarded, and should be part of the research process from the outset. As a project progresses, the data generated may well change in type and volume. It is therefore useful to envisage a DMP as a dynamic framework, which should be maintained and modified as the research advances- According to (2) the DMP needs to be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to):

- new data
- changes in consortium policies (e.g. new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent)
- changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g. new consortium members joining or old members leaving).

7.2 Metadata and data preparation

In order to make stored data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), it is not enough to store 'raw data'; they need to be properly documented and described using informative metadata. GREENPEG Partners will jointly define appropriate standards on documentation of metadata together with the set up of the software solution based data depository considering in terms of FAIR also:

- Data set description
- Standards and metadata
- Name and persistent identifier for the data sets

7.3 The GREENPEG depository

Will combine the means of an Electronic Management System (e-forum) for the internal use with an own research data depository being used as a trusted archive with an own data policy as part of the intranet. This depository will also store open access data.

7.4 The GREENPEG Data Management Plan

The latest version of the GREENPEG Data Management Plan (DMP) is written under Appendix 7. Over the course of the project, this will be updated to suit the needs of the project.

According to (2) the Commission asks the beneficiaries to submit a first version of their DMP (as a deliverable) within the first 6 months of the project.

The Commission provided a number of guiding documents on DMP which the Project Partners should also keep in mind, and which are cited in this text; e.g.:

- Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 Version 3.0, 26 July 2016
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf
- Guidelines on Implementation of *Open Access* to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020:
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf
- Open research data and data management plans
https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf
- [Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 \(pdf\)](#)

As the movement towards open data progresses, various national funding agencies have formulated policies and specified requirements for DMPs that might be informative when drawing up a DMP, for example:

Austrian ScienceFund (FWF): “Research Data Management”
<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/research-data-management/>

Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO): “Open (FAIR) Data”
<http://www.nwo.nl/en/policies/open+science/data+management>

German Research Foundation (DFG): “DFG Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data”
http://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/proposal_review_decision/applicants/research_data/index.html

Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF): “Open Research Data”
http://www.snf.ch/en/theSNSF/research_policies/open_research_data/Pages/default.aspx–The

Research Council of Norway (RCN): “Open Access to Research Data”:

https://www.forskningradet.no/en/Article/Open_access_to_research_data/1240958527698

UK Arts and Humanities Research Council(AHRC): “Data Management Plan”:

<https://ahrc.ukri.org/documents/guides/research-funding-guide1/>

(Funding Guide: “4. Application Guidance of the Funding Guide”; see also “ 5. Assessment Criteria and Peer Review”)

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020”:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

In November 2018 Science Europe published its –

“Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management”

https://www.scienceeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/SE_RDM_Practical_Guide_Final.pdf

Because practices and standards differ widely across disciplines GREENPEG will be following the Data Management Plan Template published by the European Research Council on 3rd of July 2019:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-erc-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.odt

APPENDIX (Physically and Digital)

GREENPEG Templates

- Reporting Template;
- Agenda Template;
- Meeting Minutes Template;
- Press Release Template;
- PowerPoint Presentation Template; and
- Letter Headed Paper

Appendix 1: Reporting Template

Deliverable D (WPNo)(No)

Title of Deliverable

Title of the project:	New Exploration Tools for European Pegmatite Green-Tech Resources' — 'GREENPEG'
Grant Agreement number:	869274
Funding Scheme:	HORIZON 2020 IA
Work Package:	WP(No)
Lead Editor:	Project Partner Acronym
Start date:	01.05.2020
Delivery Due Date:	Month (No)
Date of Delivery:	(Month Year)
Contact Duration:	48 months
Version:	Draft v1 / Final
Project Website:	www.greenpeg.eu

Deliverable type and dissemination level	
Report	Please indicate the dissemination level using one of the following codes: PU Public; CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) EU-RES Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC) EU-CON Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC) EU-SEC Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

2 Head line level 1

Insert text here...

1.1 Head line level 2

Insert text here...

1.1.1 Head line level 3

Insert text here...

Head line level 4 (italic)

Insert text here

Figure (no.no): insert text here

Photo (no.no): insert text here

Table (no): insert text here

Highlight message or summary here in dark blue and centric

Show bullet points this way:

- abc
- def
- ghi
- jkl

Appendix 2: Agenda Template

Meeting Agenda

CLIENT: EC	PROJECT: GREENPEG	WORK PACKAGE No:	TASK No:
MEETING : (online/ physical) (title)	ATTENDEES:	NOTES BY:	DATE:

POINTS OUTSTANDING FROM LAST MEETING

AGENDA

Appendix 3: Meeting Minutes Template

Meeting Minutes

GA No. 869274		PROJECT: GREENPEG	WORK PACKAGE No:	Task No(s):
MEETING:		PRESENT:	NOTES BY:	DATE:
ITEM:	NOTES:			ACTION / STATUS / COMMENT:
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				

Appendix 4: Press Release Template

Press Release

Place, dd/mm/yyyy

Headline: INSERT HEADLINE HERE

Insert Text Here

For more information see www.greenpeg.eu

Contacts:

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European Union GAP 869274

Appendix 5: PowerPoint Presentation Template

Event – Date – Presenter Full Name. Presenter Organisation

Last slide

Appendix 6: Letter Headed Paper

Insert Organisation Address

Our ref:
Digital ref:
Your ref:

Date: 00 Month Year

Insert Recipient's Name, Company and address

Dear

Insert the subject of the letter

|

Insert Yours sincerely or **Yours faithfully**
for **GREENPEG**

NAME
Title
Email Address

Appendix 7: Data Management Plan

ABREVIATIONS

API: Application Programming Interface
CA: Consortium Agreement
DMP: Data Management Plan
DOI: Digital Object Identifier
EC: European Commission
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA: Grant Agreement
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
IPR: Intellectual Property Rights
OA: Open Access
ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot

1 INTRODUCTION

Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement sets out detailed legal requirements on open access to scientific publications where each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Furthermore, the European Commission requires an Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) under Horizon 2020 call to enable open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. There are two main pillars to the Pilot: developing a Data Management Plan (DMP) and providing open access to research data, if possible. The ORDP takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions.

2 TYPES OF DATA COVERED BY THE OPEN RESEARCH DATA PILOT

'Underlying data' (the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications), including the associated metadata (i.e. metadata describing the research data deposited), as soon as possible.

Any **other data** (for instance curated data not directly attributable to a publication, or primary data), including the associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the DMP – that is, according to the individual judgement by each project/grantee.

Literature review and information of existing articles or documents that are included in GREENPEG material will not be subject to ORDP since this information is not produced under the project unless there is some uniqueness in the final product. For instance, if we prepare a summary of geochemistry in one of the test sites using public data, these data will not be subject to ORDP unless the data is further developed and presented in a different manner than in the original document.

3 FAIR DATA

GREENPEG beneficiaries are committed to make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR). Provisions to comply with the FAIR principles are provided in the following sections:

3.1 Making data findable

The GREENPEG project has a strong intention and focus on the findability of project results and data within the project group, but equally important also to external users, researchers and stakeholders. The project has therefore established a simple and easy-to-remember web portal at www.greenpeg.eu and an e-forum platform for project internal data exchange and communication. For open access, all publications, all data, primary and curated data, final data products, created within the scope of the GREENPEG project will be subsequently uploaded and stored in an open research repository for long-term preservation.

GREENPEG will use by default OpenAIRE's repository, Zenodo (<https://www.zenodo.org/>), an OpenAIRE and CERN collaboration, which allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, with the aim of supporting the EC's Open Data policy by providing a set of tools for funded research. ZENODO has the feature of so-called 'Communities', where users can collect related content in one place. Similar to a number of other H2020 projects, the GREENPEG project has created a community under the name GREENPEG <https://zenodo.org/communities/greenpeg-project/>. Regarding privacy issues, the Zenodo repository allows the publisher to restrict data access (open, closed, restricted, and embargoed), asking for the data owner's approval before downloading them. Zenodo and some other repositories as well as many academic publishers also facilitate linking publications and underlying data through persistent identifiers and data citations.

Figure 3.1 Screenshot from the GREENPEG community on the Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org/communities/greenpeg-project/>. The upload of data, products and publications enable open access and reuse of research data generated by GREENPEG.

To support project awareness and data findability, visibility of GREENPEG is crucial to our public relation strategy. Therefore, links to the GREENPEG research repository will not only be published on our webpage, but also on relevant platforms like the Raw Material Information System (RMIS)

<https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/?page=rmkg> and *GREENPEG researchgate group*
<https://www.researchgate.net/project/GREENPEG-EU-H2020-GA869274> .

3.2 Making data openly accessible

GREENPEG has a general open data policy regulated by the project's GA and in line with the Horizon 2020 regulations. GREENPEG chose the OpenAIRE free-of-charge ZENODO research repository as platform for open access to data and publications from the GREENPEG project. All publications – in refereed journals, but also conference proceedings, reports, and other documentation – will also be stored in ZENODO, and they can be searched for via all usual metadata.

The GREENPEG open access mandate comprises 2 steps:

- a) depositing content in GREENPEG ORD repository on ZENODO
- b) providing open access to them.

a) Repository beneficiaries must deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in the GREENPEG community at the ZENODO repository for scientific publications (<https://www.zenodo.org/communities/greenpeg-project>) If applicable, the data and products shall be provided in GIS database format including all existing metadata for the individual datasets. Any needed restriction in access to the data is evaluated before final publication, in accordance with ethical aspects and with protection of personal data (GDPR).

Upload of data must be done upon publication. (The latest acceptable time to deposit a publication is the date of publication). Repository for scientific publications is an online archive. Institutional, subject-based and centralised repositories are all acceptable choices. The Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) is the recommended entry point for researchers to determine what repository to choose.

b) After depositing publications/data and products, beneficiaries must ensure open access to those publications via the chosen repository.

3.2.1 *Open Access to publication*

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. Open access to scientific publications means free online access for any user. To meet this requirement, beneficiaries must, at the very least, ensure that any scientific peer-reviewed publications can be read online, downloaded and printed. Since any further rights - such as the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine - make publications more useful, beneficiaries should make every effort to provide as many of these options as possible.

3.2.2 *Open Access to data*

The Commission has enabled access to, and reuse of, research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects through the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). The legal requirements for participating projects are set out in Article 29.3 of the Model Grant Agreement, included by default in the Grant Agreement.

The ORDP applies primarily to the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications. More particularly, according to the H2020 online manual, ORDP refers to the right to access and reuse digital research data under the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement.

In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images.

3.3 Making data interoperable

GREENPEG realises that common data and metadata standards and formats are a key aspect for technological and semantic data operability. Standardisation makes the data discoverable, and this way promotes international and interdisciplinary access to, and use of, research data. To ensure correct and proper use and interpretation of the GREENPEG data by the owners and re-users, the use of standardised vocabularies and ontologies is also necessary.

3.3.1 File formats

The format and software in which research data are created depend on how researchers choose to collect and analyse data, often determined by discipline-specific standards and customs. Ensuring long-term usability of the GREENPEG data requires consideration of the most appropriate software and file formats. If applicable, GIS database format is well adapted and universal for most datasets. However, for other datasets discipline-specific standards shall be applied. A selection of such formats is given in Table 1 (Appendix 1), listing the file formats, broken down by thematic data type, that will be used in the GREENPEG consortium. Given the broad spectrum of data types, there is a large range of domain-specific formats for data sharing and thematic systems that can serve redistribution of those data. All data shall be collected and visualised within GIS software packages (example in Fig. 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Example for data loading and visualisation in a GIS software, which stores also Metadata. Most data can be exported in GIS databases

All datasets stored at the e-forum and ZENODO will include metadata: discovery and technical metadata that defines the what, where, when, why, and how data of the data. Where appropriate, the data creators will assign Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) or a Persistent URL (PURL) to their datasets. As well as all GREENPEG metadata, all GREENPEG documentation (reports, publications, etc.) will be

stored in ZENODO. Users can search via keywords in ZENODO, and from there be directed to the dataset and use it.

The approaches for storing, finding, and accessing the data generated within the GREENPEG projects are still under discussion. The expectations on FAIR data will be made clear to all that use and provide the GREENPEG services.

3.4 Making data re-useable

3.4.1 Quality control

For the GREENPEG research data collection, quality control of the data can happen at various stages during the quality assurance process. An initial quality control is needed at the local level and early in the collection process. Additional controls will take place at a later stage of the data life-cycle. A final quality control of metadata takes place during its input into ZENODO.

The initial quality control of the data, during data collection, is the primary responsibility of the GREENPEG data creator/owner, who must ensure that the recorded data reflect the facts, responses, observations and events. The quality of the data collection methods used strongly influences data quality and documenting in detail how data are collected provides evidence of such quality. Errors can also occur during data entry. Data are digitised, transcribed, entered in a database or spreadsheet, or coded. Here, quality is ensured by standardised and consistent procedures for data entry with clear instructions such procedures and the data collection methods are defined in detail in the Project Management Plan (D1.1).

3.4.2 Metadata

The use of common data and metadata standards and formats are a key aspect for technological and semantic data operability, allowing the data to be discoverable and hence promoting international and interdisciplinary access to, and use of, research data. Standard dictionaries of metadata will be used for all data types produced by the data creators. In cases where the data are already accessible through local online databases, a web link to these local systems will be included in the dataset description. Any unique or uncommon metadata keywords will be mapped to a more common standard during the import to the ZENODO. A technical quality control will ensure that all required information is included.

Different communities and disciplines develop and adopt various metadata standards and/or practices for the management of their research data and materials. GREENPEG has a suggested content for Metadata (Figure 2), which is considered as a guideline, but does not reflect a complete list.

GREENPEG metadata will rather attempt to follow discipline-specific standards but at the very least, metadata will be given as a text-file following the guidelines shown in Figure 3.3.

Metadata/Readme file:		Coordinate System:	
General:	[to fill in: Data type]:	Name	Example: http://geo.ngu.no/GeosciencePortal/search
Dataset title	Survey name	Extents	
Orig. file name	Acquisition contractor	(East, West, North, South)	
Project	Line spacing (m)		
Acqu. Date	Line direction (deg cw)		
Description	Tie line spacing (m)		
Web Url	Total line kilometers (km)		
Supporting documents	Vessel type		
Keywords	Instrument 1		
	Instrument 2		
Data:	Instrument 3		
Data source	Instrument 4		
Data format	Additional instruments		
Classification	Positioning method		
Restrictions	Survey start date		
Administration contractor	Survey end date		
Processing contractor	Survey comment		
Metadata created by			
Metadata creation date			

Open for additional information!

Figure 3.3 Guidelines for metadata format, taken from the GREENPEG *e-forum*.

3.4.3 File naming

A structured data storage is essential for proper and secure storage of data files and records. For any file-based storage this includes clear and unambiguous file naming, the use of proper versioning, clear and intuitive folder structure. The use of a standard file naming convention per data type, and a clear versioning will be encouraged by GREENPEG, and in some cases is ensured by use of community services.

Within GREENPEG a set of recommendations for file naming for the various thematic data types is already drawn up (Figure 3.4.) and maintained in the GREENPEG *e-forum*.

Data type:		Scale:	Data progress:	
MAG – magnetic	Pv – province	RAW – Raw data	Borehole logs: SuS –susceptibility Dens – density TGam – Total gamma SGam – spectral gamma OPTV – Optical televiewer ATV –acoustic televiewer Res – Electric resistivity Cher – Chargeability Lith – Lithology Collar – Collar information	Enhancement/Filtering applied: TF – magnetic total field RTP – reduced to pole FA – freeair gravity BG – Bouguer gravity MICLEV – microlevelled HP200 – Highpass filter 200 m LP200 – Lowpass filter 200 m BP200 – 1000 Bandpass200-1000 m FVD – first vertical derivative SVD – 2nd vert. derivative AS – analytical signal TDR – TILT derivative Mig – migrated AGC – automatic gain controlled
GRAV – gravity	D – district	Pr – Processed data		
RAD – radiometry	P – prospect			
U – uranium	Organization (data made/compiled by):			
Th – thorium	NGU – Geological Survey of Norway			
K – potassium	TERRA – Terra Tec			
Cs – cesium (before 1986!)	UIO – ...			
AEM – airborne EM	→ Organisation name as in GA			
MS – multi spectral	Status:			
HS – hyper spectral	O – open			
ERT – Electric resistivity tomo	R – restricted			
DD – DipoleDipole	Platform:			
GP - GradientPlus	S – satellite			
GPR – Ground penetrating radar	A – airborne			
PES – Piezoelectric seismic	D – drone			
AMT – Audio Magnetotelluric	G – groundborne			
SEIS – seismic	Data structure:			
inSAR	I – Grid			
LIDar	L – Profiles/Line data			
Bed – Bedrock map	N – map scale			

File Name Example (Keep order, skip option if not applicable), same applies to :
 DataType_Location_Scale_Organization_Status_Platform_DataStructure_Dataprogress_BoreholeLogs_Enhancement_#NAME#.*

Figure 3.4 File name nomenclature, taken from the GREENPEG *e-forum*.

4 ALLOCATION OF REOURCES AND DATA SECURITY

All research data produced during GREENPEG will be stored in the GREENPEG project’s e-forum, which is a separated Network Attached Storage (NAS) hosted and physically deployed within Europe.

A general guideline to increase data security is given to all project members

Some suggestions for security of computer systems and files:

- Locking computer systems with a password and installing a firewall system;
- Protecting servers by power surge protection systems through line interactive uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems;
- Implementing password protection of, and controlled access to, data files, e.g., no access, read only, read and write or administrator-only permission;
- Controlling access to restricted materials with encryption;
- Imposing non-disclosure agreements for managers or users of confidential data;
- Not sending personal or confidential data via email or other file transfer means without first encrypting them;
- Destroying data in a consistent manner when needed;
- Remember that file sharing services such as Google Docs or Dropbox may not be that secure.

(From the UK Data Archive)

5 ETHICAL ASPECTS

GREENPEG will be compliant with the EMBRC ethics review guidelines, and will follow the guidelines of ENVRI+ (an H2020 programme: Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures: <http://www.envriplus.eu/>). Furthermore, GREENPEG will take measures to be compliant with the EU regulations regarding the protection of personal data (<http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection>).

ANNEX of the DMP:

Datatype	Formats	Comment
Geophysics raster	geoTiff, Geosoft grd, ER2, csv	
Geophysics points	csv, xlsx	
Geophysics profiles	csv	
Petrophysics	csv, xlsx	
Geochemistry	csv	
Geology line	ESRi shp,	
Geology maps	Geopackage, geotiff, png	
Gamma ray spectroscopy	csv, json	
Hyperspectral imaging	Geotiff, jpg, raw	
Geochemical mineral maps	tiff, png	
...		

Standard keywords to be used consistently with GREENPEG content (publications, reports, metadata, etc.). These keywords (Table X) represent a minimum requirement, additional keywords are not excluded.

- Aeromagnetics
- Airborne geophysics
- Droneborne geophysics
- Austria
- EM
- Geochemistry
- Geology
- Geophysics
- Gravity
- High-resolution
- Ireland
- Leinster
- MAG
- Norway
- Pegmatite
- Quartz
- Radiometry/RAD
- Resistivity
- Tysfjord
- Wolfsberg
- Hyperspectral imaging
- Gamma ray spectroscopy
- Soil
- Stream sediment
- Whole-rock
- Geochemical mineral map

REFERENCES

- (1) Open Research Data and Data Management Plans Information for ERC grantees by the ERC Scientific Council – Version 3.1, 3 July 2019
- (2) Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 Version 3.0, 26 July 2016
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf
- (3) Guidelines on Implementation of *Open Access* to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020:
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf
- (4) Open research data and data management plans
https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf
- (5) [Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 \(pdf\)](#)
- (6) How to develop a Media Partnership
<https://bizfluent.com/13725244/press-releases-uses-results-for-small-business-owners>
- (7) Press Releases: Uses & Results For Small Business Owners
<https://bizfluent.com/13725244/press-releases-uses-results-for-small-business-owners>
- (8) Communication Tool Kit by EASME
<https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/section/communication-toolkit>
- (9) The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf
- (10) How to communicate your project
https://ec.europa.eu/easme/sites/easme-site/files/howtocommunicateyourproject_vertical.pdf

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